

RESEARCH ARTICLE

The influence of palm fiber reinforcement on the cement content of vegetated concrete substrate under the condition of equal strength

Xiaole Huang¹, Xue An¹, Gang Zeng^{1,2*}, Shiyuan Xiong¹, Xiaojun Sun³

1 School of Architectural Engineering, Xiangyang Vocational and Technical College, Xiangyang, China,

2 School of Civil Engineering and Architecture, Hubei University of Arts and Science, Xiangyang, China,

3 School of Chemical & Environmental Engineering, Pingdingshan University, Pingdingshan, China

* gangz@hbuas.edu.cn

OPEN ACCESS

Citation: Huang X, An X, Zeng G, Xiong S, Sun X (2024) The influence of palm fiber reinforcement on the cement content of vegetated concrete substrate under the condition of equal strength. PLoS ONE 19(10): e0311928. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928>

Editor: Paul Awoyera, Covenant University, NIGERIA

Received: June 2, 2024

Accepted: September 26, 2024

Published: October 17, 2024

Copyright: © 2024 Huang et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Data Availability Statement: All relevant data are within the article.

Funding: This research was sponsored by the funds of Xiangyang Innovation and Development Joint Fund project of Hubei Province Natural Science Foundation with grant number 2024AFD036, Hubei Provincial Engineering Research Center of Slope Habitat Construction Technique Using Cement-based Materials with grant number 2022SNJ08, and Research Project of Hubei Provincial Department of Education with

Abstract

Vegetated concrete substrate (VCS) is a kind of ecological cemented soil, which has very wide application prospect in high and steep rock slope eco-protection. Cement is an important component of VCS, but it has high energy consumption and environmental pollution. Fiber reinforcement plays a positive role in improving the mechanical properties of soil, and its use as a substitute for cement content in VCS under the condition of equal strength is rarely investigated. In this study, the unconsolidated-undrained (UU) triaxial compression test of unreinforced substrate as blank control samples (BCS) and reinforced substrate as fiber reinforced samples (FRS) were carried out. The test results showed that the stress-strain curve of VCS can be divided into compaction stage, elastic stage, plastic stage and strain hardening stage. The average peak strength increased by 34.3kPa, 53.6kPa, 218kPa and 81.8kPa as cement content of VCS was 0%, 4%, 6% and 8%, respectively. The relationship between the peak strength and cement content of VCS could be better fit by Boltzmann function. The mathematical model of fiber instead of cement in VCS under the condition of equal strength was established. It is found that there is a critical point of cement content according to the mathematical model. The cement of VCS can be completely replaced by palm fiber as the cement content is less than the critical point. While the cement content is higher than the critical point, the cement of VCS can be partially replaced by palm fiber. The decrease of average cement content was 17.23%, 19.00%, 24.27% and 25.34% with 0.2%, 0.4%, 0.6% and 0.8% fiber content in reinforced substrate, respectively. The theoretical method and interpolation method for fiber substitute cement content of VCS under equal strength condition were proposed, which can provide technical guidance for ecological slope protection engineering practice of vegetated concrete.

1 Introduction

Earthwork excavation is very common in transportation, water conservancy, mining and other engineering practices, which will not only destroy the ecological environment, but also

grant number B2023518. The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Competing interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

form a large number of exposed slopes [1–3]. These ecological wounds are difficult to recover under natural conditions, and there are geological hazards such as landslides and collapses [4,5]. Vegetation concrete slope protection technology is widely used in ecological restoration of exposed slope [6–8]. The technology is to spray the mixture of planting substrate and planting green seeds onto the slope surface to form a shallow stable layer of slope with a thickness of about 10cm, which has good ecological and landscape effects [9–11].

VCS is the core of ecological slope protection technology of vegetated concrete [12]. VCS is a mixture of cement, soil, organic matter, ecological amendments and water in a certain proportion [13]. The substrate must not only have conditions that facilitate for plant growth, but also need to have appropriate strength [14]. The cohesiveness and strength of VCS are formed by the hydration reaction of cement. However, cement has a certain alkaline stress effect on plant growth. The higher the cement content, the greater the stress effect of cement on plants [8]. The reduction of cement content in the substrate is beneficial to plant growth and slope ecological restoration from an ecological point of view [13]. In addition, the cement industry has become a major emitter of carbon dioxide due to its inherent raw material structure and production process limitations [15,16]. Each 1t of cement clinker produced will emit 0.894 ~ 1.215t CO₂. At present, the cement industry accounts for about 13.5% of the country's total carbon emissions in China. As one of the world's largest cement producers and consumers, the cement industry has become a key area for China to achieve the goal of "carbon peak and carbon neutrality".

The reduction of the amount of cement in the substrate has great economic and environmental benefits. However, the strength of the substrate also decreases with the reduction of the cement content, which will affect the stability of the substrate on the slope. Therefore, it is particularly necessary to reduce the amount of cement by adding appropriate reinforcement materials under the premise that the strength of the substrate meets the requirements. Plam fiber can not only improve strength and other engineering mechanical properties of the substrate, but also contribute to the recycling of waste resources [17–22]. Fiber can improve the strength and durability of concrete [23–25], but there are few reports on the content of fiber instead of cement. Therefore, palm fiber is selected as the reinforced material of the substrate in this study, and the strength of 4 unreinforced substrate samples and 16 reinforced substrate samples are determined by unconsolidated undrained triaxial shear test. The substitution effect of plam fiber on cement content in VCS is studied, and the method of substituting plam fiber for cement is put forward based on the condition of equal strength.

2 Material and methods

2.1 Materials

The VCS is composed of soil, organic matter, cement and habitat modifying agent in this study. The soil is collected from a farmland in Yichang of Hubei Province, China. The organic matter is pine sawdust purchased in the market. The particle percentage of soil and sawdust is shown in Table 1. It can be seen from Table 1 that the soil texture is silty sand (SM) containing fine grained soil. The cement is P-C 32.5 composite Portland cement, and its physical and mechanical indexes are shown in Table 2. The function of habitat modifying agent is to

Table 1. Particle percentages of the soil and pine sawdust.

Particle size /mm	≥2	2~1	1~0.5	0.5~0.25	0.25~0.1	0.1~0.074	<0.074
Soil	0	21.34	25.46	19.88	16.88	8.17	8.27
Pine sawdust	12.06	12.06	40.75	24.76	7.01	3.34	0

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928.t001>

Table 2. The basic parameters of cement.

Cement	SO ₃ (%)	MgO (%)	Cl ⁻ (%)	Initial setting time(min)	Final setting time(min)	Rupture strength (MPa)		Compressive strength (MPa)	
						3d	28d	3d	28d
P.C 32.5	≤3.5	≤6.0	≤0.06	≥45	≤600	≥2.5	≥5.5	≥10	≥32.5

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928.t002>

activate the substrate to facilitate plant growth, and the detailed information can visit the official website of Hubei Runzhi Ecological Technology Co., LTD (www.runzhist.com).

The reinforced material is plam fiber in this study. The physical and mechanical indexes of plam fiber are shown in Table 3. As can be seen from Table 3, plam fiber is a kind of medium strength and high elongation fiber.

2.2 Sample preparation

2.2.1 Test scheme. The weight of each component in VCS is usually determined by the dry weight of soil in the practice of ecological slope protection engineering. The content of sawdust and ecological amendments is set to a fixed value, 6% and 4% of the dry soil mass respectively. The cement content is set at 0%, 4%, 6% and 8% of the dry soil mass according to the references. The plam fiber content is based on the dry weight of mixtures such as soil, sawdust, cement and ecological amendments in this study. The content of plam fiber shall not exceed 0.8% of the dry weight of the mixture according to the pre-mix test. Therefore, the plam fiber content is set to four levels, 0.2%, 0.4%, 0.6% and 0.8% of the dry weight of the mixture. The BCS is with no addition of fibers and contains 0%, 4%, 6% and 8% cement. The FRS is manufactured by adding plam fiber into VCS in the proportion of 0.2%, 0.4%, 0.6% and 0.8% respectively. The test scheme of this study is shown in Table 4.

The particle size distribution curves of the BCS is showed in Fig 1. It can be seen from Fig 1 that the particle size distribution range of BCS is wide and the curve is relatively gentle.

The characteristic particle sizes d_{60} , d_{30} , d_{10} as well as their inhomogeneity coefficient C_u and curvature coefficient C_c of BCS can be obtained from Fig 1, and the results are shown in Table 5. As can be seen from Table 5, C_u is greater than 10 and C_c is in the range of 1–3, which indicates that the BCS belong to well-graded soil.

2.2.2 Sample preparation. The soil is naturally air-dried, ground and sieved by 2mm [26]. The sawdust should be air-dried and screened by 2mm before sample preparation. The plam fiber is cut and broken to less than 2mm. The specimen size is a cylinder with diameter of 39.1mm and height of 80mm. The initial moisture content and dry density of VCS are determined by engineering experience to be 20% and 1.35g/cm³, respectively [13]. Each component of VCS is initially weighed (with an accuracy of 0.01 g) according to the requirements and mixed together, then the water required is added and mixed with the dry mixture. The watered mixture is stored in an airtight container for 30 min, so that the water is fully and evenly absorbed by all components. The mixed material is evenly pressed into the cylinder sampler in 3 times one by one. The quality inspection is carried out on the sample after compaction is completed, and samples with a quality error of less than ± 1% are considered qualified [13].

Table 3. Physical and mechanical parameters of palm fiber.

Diameter /μm	Length /cm	Elasticity modulus /GPa	Tensile strength /MPa	Elongation ratio /%	Acid and alkali resistance
199~539	2.0	0.44~1.09	89~222	14.68~23.45	Strong

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928.t003>

Table 4. The test scheme of this study.

Group	Composition of the substrate sample								
	Content of each component of the substrate (%)				Fiber content (W_f /%)				
	Soil	Cement	Pine sawdust	Habitat modifying agent	BCS	FRS			
I	100	0	6	4	0.0	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8
II	100	4			0.0	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8
III	100	6			0.0	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8
IV	100	8			0.0	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928.t004>

The weight of each sample after pressed in cylinder mould is about 158.5g. The prepared samples are cured in a moist chamber for 7 days before they are subjected to subsequent testing. The process of sample preparation is showed in Fig 2.

2.3 Method

2.3.1 Test method. The consolidation and drainage effects of the VCS on the side slope are not obvious, which is mainly due to its thin thickness. Therefore, the unconsolidated undrained (UU) triaxial test method is used to measure the strength of the VCS. Strain controlled triaxial shear instrument is used in the test equipment, which can automatically record the deviatorial stress and axial load of the sample. The confining pressure is set at 50kPa and the shear rate is 0.9 mm/min. The failure criterion of the sample is the peak point of

Fig 1. Particle size distribution curves of BCS.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928.g001>

Table 5. Characteristic particle sizes, nhomogeneity coefficient and curvature coefficient of BCS.

Cement content/%	d_{60}	d_{30}	d_{10}	C_u	C_c
0	0.634	0.24	0.04	15.85	2.27
4	0.63	0.225	0.030	21.00	2.68
6	0.626	0.221	0.028	22.36	2.79
8	0.621	0.220	0.023	27.00	2.80

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928.t005>

deviational stress. If there is no peak point, the peak strength is the deviational stress as the axial strain reaches 15% [13].

2.3.2 Analytical method. The effect of fiber reinforcement on the strength of the substrate is analyzed according to the UU triaxial test results, and the functional relationship between the strength of the blank substrate and the strength of the reinforced substrate and the cement content is established respectively. Based on the principle of equal strength, the substitution effect of fiber on cement content of substrate is analyzed under the premise of equal strength.

3 Results and analysis

3.1 Stress-strain curves of VCS

The stress-strain curves of the four groups are shown in Fig 3. In Fig 3, the specimens with a fiber content of 0.0% are identified as BCS (blank control samples), while the specimens with fiber contents of 0.2%, 0.4%, 0.6%, and 0.8% are designated as FRS (fiber reinforced samples).

Fig 2. The process of sample preparation.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928.g002>

Fig 3. Stress-strain curves of VCS samples (A) Group I (B) Group II (C) Group III (D) Group IV.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928.g003>

As can be seen from Fig 3, the stress-strain curves of the four groups of specimens are basically the same, which can be characterized of four typical phases, namely initial deformation, elastic deformation, yielding, and hardening stage or softening stage. The compaction characteristics of the specimens in group I are the most obvious and the compaction feature become more and more obvious as the fiber content increases. In addition, the deviational stress of the

BCS increased with the increase of cement content and their brittleness became obviously enhanced simultaneously. The FRS hold the increasing stresses with fiber contents and their brittle characteristics were significantly improved at the same time. In the same group, the BCS has the most obvious brittle characteristics and the brittleness of the FRS are gradually weakened with the increase of fiber content. The stress-strain curves of group I, II, III and IV are characterized as strain hardening type, weak strain hardening type, ideal elastic-plastic strain and strain softening strain, respectively.

3.2 Ultimate strength of VCS

The results of the ultimate strength of the four groups of specimens are shown in Fig 4.

As can be seen in Fig 4, compared with group I, the ultimate strength of the BCS in group II did not increase significantly while the ultimate strength of III and IV increase by 3.7 times and 8.1 times, respectively. The trend of the ultimate strength of the FRS is consistent with that of the BCS. Compared to the BCS (sample with a fiber content of 0.0%), the average increases in ultimate strength for the FRS (samples with fiber contents of 0.2%, 0.4%, 0.6%, and 0.8%)

Fig 4. Relationship between ultimate strength and fiber contents of VCS.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928.g004>

across the four groups are 34.3 kPa, 53.6 kPa, 218 kPa, and 81.8 kPa, respectively. The average increase of the ultimate strength first increased and then decreased with the increase of cement content and the values were 57%, 65%, 77% and 15%, respectively. When the cement content is 6%, the FRS has the largest increase of the ultimate strength. This is because that the strengths of VCS are affected by the coupling actions of fiber and cement. When the cement content is zero or low (groups I and II), the reinforcement potential of the fiber is not fully developed because the substrates would be weakly cemented in term of the relatively low hydrate products generated. As the substrates become increasingly improved (groups III), the optimum potential would be achieved when the load-bearing capacity of substrate is compatible to that of fiber. While when the cement content is high (group IV), the capacity of the substrates becomes far higher than the potential limit of fiber, the potential of fiber would be partially inhibited and incompletely achieved [13].

3.3 Relationships between ultimate strength and cement content of VCS

Based on the results of the four groups of specimens' ultimate strength, the linear function (LF), the exponential function (EF) and the Boltzmann function (BF) under the growth/sigmoidal option of the Origin 7.0 software were used to fit the experimental data for math model. The fitting results are shown in Table 6. The expression of BF is shown in Eq 1.

$$q_{max} = \frac{a_1 - a_2}{1 + e^{\frac{x_c - x_0}{d}}} + a_2 \tag{1}$$

In Eq (1), q_{max} is the ultimate strength of the specimen and X_c is the cement content. The characters including a_1 , a_2 , x_0 and d are the regression coefficients of the fitting function, where x_0 is the inflection point, $q_{max} = a_1$ and $q_{max} = a_2$ are the two asymptotes of the fitting curve.

As can be seen from Table 6, the correlation coefficients of LF and EF ranged from 0.766 to 0.821 and 0.858 to 0.869, with average values of 0.806 and 0.864, respectively. In contrast, the range of correlation coefficient of BF (0.975–0.994) and its average value (0.985) are much higher than those of LF and EF, which means that the BF can better reflect the relationship between the ultimate strength and cement content of the VCS.

Fig 5 shows the relationship between the ultimate strength and cement content of the VCS fitted by BF.

It can be seen from Fig 5 that the fitting curves of BF are S-shaped. When the cement content is less than 4%, the ultimate strengths of VCS increase slowly with the increase of cement content. When the cement content ranges from 4% to 6%, the ultimate strength of VCS enters a rapid growth stage. However, with a further increase in cement content (more than 6%), the growth rate of the ultimate strength has the trend of decreasing.

Table 6. The parameters and correlation coefficients of master curves.

$W_f/\%$	Parameters of BF				LF	EF	Correlation coefficients		
	a_1	a_2	x_0	d			BF	LF	EF
0.0	60.3	548.4	6.1595	0.4	$q_{max} = 58.047X_c - 17.637$	$q_{max} = 46.727e^{0.2826X_c}$	0.993	0.766	0.866
0.2	72.8	593.3	5.3885	0.4	$q_{max} = 67.011X_c - 0.2514$	$q_{max} = 59.644e^{0.2808X_c}$	0.975	0.815	0.865
0.4	90.6	615.1	5.33323	0.4	$q_{max} = 67.917X_c + 19.323$	$q_{max} = 75.891e^{0.2565X_c}$	0.975	0.821	0.869
0.6	100.7	636.2	5.1924	0.4	$q_{max} = 70.917X_c + 31.223$	$q_{max} = 85.623e^{0.2496X_c}$	0.986	0.817	0.862
0.8	114.5	676.0	5.093	0.4	$q_{max} = 75.684X_c + 44.846$	$q_{max} = 98.725e^{0.2424X_c}$	0.994	0.811	0.858

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928.t006>

Fig 5. Fitting relationships between the ultimate strength and cement content of VCS.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928.g005>

4 Effect of palm fiber as a substitute for cement in VCS under the condition of equal strength

In this research, the equal-strength function relationships between the VCS and the FRS are established on the assumption that the self-stability of the FRS could meet the engineering requirements as long as the FRS has the same strength with the BCS (Fig 6).

In Fig 6, A and C are the points on AB and CD curves where the cement content is 0%, respectively. B and D are the points on AB and CD curves where the cement content is 8%, respectively. E is the point at 4% cement content on AB curve. G is the intersection point of the line parallel to the horizontal axis and the CD curve. F is the intersection point of the line parallel to the horizontal axis and the AB curve. F is the critical point on AB curve and the corresponding cement content is recorded as $X_{c(F)}$.

Because the cement content of VCS in engineering practice ranges from 4% to 8%, in this study only the equal strength equations in the segment of EB curve of the BCS were established. The EB curve is divided into EF segment and FB segment with F point as the boundary. And the strength corresponding to the EF curve are lower than that of the C point ($X_c = 0\%$, $W_f = 0.2\%, 0.4\%, 0.6\%, 0.8\%$) on FRS curve. Combined with the variation principle of the ultimate strength of BCS, the strength of FRS can be equal to that of the BCS by keeping the cement content constant ($X_c = 0\%$) and reducing the fiber content appropriately. In contrast, there is an equal strength on CD curve of the FRS to every strength on FB curve of the BCS, which means that the equal strength model of the BCS and the FRS can be established directly through the Boltzmann functions of them. The methods and steps about how to construct the iso-strength functional relationship between the BCS and the FRS for the EF and FB sections are as follows.

Using the strength fitting curve (AB) of the BCS as standard, and taking the fitting curve (CD) of the FRS with a fiber content of 0.4% as an example, the establishment process of the equal strength function relationships are as follows.

Fig 6. Diagram of cement content of the relationship between BCS and FRS.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928.g006>

4.1 The equal strength functional relationship between the BCS of EF segment and the FRS

The equal strength functional relationship between the BCS of the EF segment and the FRS is established as follows.

Step 1: Using linear function to fit the relationship between the ultimate strength $q_{max(1)}$ and the fiber content of the FRS (Group I, Fig 4). The result is shown in Formula (2).

Step 2: Substitute the master curve parameters of the BCS in Table 6 into Formula (1) to obtain the functional relationship between the ultimate strength $q_{max(0)}$ and the cement content $X_{c(0)}$ of the BCS. The fitting result is shown in Formula (3).

Step 3: Unit Formula (2) and Formula (3) under the condition of equal strength for the BCS and the FRS ($q_{max(1)} = q_{max(0)}$), and the relationship between the cement content $X_{c(0)}$ of the BCS and the fiber content W_f of the FRS is shown in Formula (4).

$$q_{max(1)} = 68.15 \times W_f + 60.52, R^2 = 0.9943 \tag{2}$$

Table 7. The one-to-one relationship between the $X_{c(0)}$ of the BCS and the W_f of the FRS on EF curve.

Cement Content of the BCS $X_{c(0)}$ /%	4.0	4.2	4.4	4.6	4.8	5.0	5.2
Fiber content of the FRS W_f /%	0.03	0.05	0.08	0.14	0.23	0.37	0.59

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928.t007>

$$q_{\max(0)} = 584.4 - \frac{488.1}{1 + e^{\frac{X_{c(0)} - 6.1595}{0.4}}}, (4 \leq X_{c(0)} < X_{c(F)}) \tag{3}$$

$$W_f = \frac{487.88 - 488.1 / (1 + e^{\frac{X_{c(0)} - 6.1595}{0.4}})}{68.15} \tag{4}$$

It can be seen from the Formula (4) that under the condition of equal strength, when the cement content of the VCS is low, the cement can be completely replaced by palm fibers.

Table 7 shows the one-to-one relationship between cement content $X_{c(0)}$ of the BCS and fiber content W_f of the FRS for some points on EF curve under the condition of equal strength, which can be used as a reference for engineering practice.

4.2 The equal strength functional relationship between the BCS of FB segment and the FRS

The specific steps for establishing the equal strength relationship between the BCS of the FB section and the FRS are as follows.

Step 1: Substitute the master curve parameters of the BCS in Table 6 into Formula (1) to obtain the functional relationship between the ultimate strength $q_{\max(0)}$ of the BCS and the cement content $X_{c(0)}$. The result is shown in Formula (5).

Step 2: Substitute the master curve parameters of the FRS in Table 6 into the Formula (1) to obtain the functional relationship between the ultimate strength $q_{\max(2)}$ of the FRS and the cement content $X_{c(2)}$. The result is shown in the Formula (6).

Step 3: The equal strength model of the BCS of the FB section and the FRS can be obtained by uniting the Formulas (5) and (6) ($q_{\max(0)} = q_{\max(2)}$), and the results is shown in the Formula (7).

$$q_{\max(0)} = 584.4 - \frac{488.1}{1 + e^{\frac{X_{c(0)} - 6.1595}{0.4}}}, (X_{c(F)} \leq X_{c(0)} \leq 8) \tag{5}$$

$$q_{\max(2)} = \frac{a_1 - a_2}{1 + e^{\frac{X_{c(2)} - x_0}{d}}} + a_2 \tag{6}$$

$$X_{c(2)} = d \times \ln \frac{a_1 - 60.3 + (a_1 - 584.4) \times e^{\frac{X_{c(0)} - 6.1595}{0.4}}}{60.3 - a_2 + (584.4 - a_2) \times e^{\frac{X_{c(0)} - 6.1595}{0.4}}} + x_0 \tag{7}$$

In Formula (7), the values of a_1 , a_2 and x_0 can be scraped from Table 6. As we can see from Fig 6 that when the cement content in the BCS ranges from $X_{c(F)}$ to 8 (FB segment), the cement in BCS can be partially replaced by the palm fiber under the condition of equal strength, and Formula (7) gives the corresponding relationship between the cement content $X_{c(0)}$ of the BCS and the cement content $X_{c(2)}$ of the FRS.

4.3 Effect of palm fiber reinforcement on cement content for VCS under the condition of equal strength

It can be seen from the above analysis that when the cement content in BCS is low (EF section on AB curve), the cement in BCS can be completely replaced by palm fiber with a stunning reduction of 100%. When the cement content in BCS is high (FB section on AB curve), the cement content in BCS can be partially replaced by palm fiber. Under the condition of equal strength, the reduction quantity of the cement content of the BCS could be calculated by the Formula (8).

$$\Delta X_{c(0)} = X_{c(0)} - X_{c(2)} \tag{8}$$

Table 8 shows the cement content $X_{c(0)}$ of the BCS, the cement content $X_{c(2)}$ of the FRS, the reduction of cement content ΔX_c and the reduction margin of cement content $\Delta X_c/X_{c(0)}$ under the condition of equal strength.

As can be seen from Table 8, the cement content $X_{c(2)}$ in FRS with a certain fiber content has an increasing trend with the cement content $X_{c(0)}$ in BCS. With the cement content increase, the reduction quantity of cement content ΔX_c and its reduction margin $\Delta X_c/X_{c(0)}$ decrease first and then increase. At a certain cement content of BCS, there are various choice of FRS with different fiber content at the same strength. The cement content $X_{c(2)}$ of the FRS gradually decreases with the increase of fiber content, while the reduction quantity ΔX_c and its reduction margin $\Delta X_c/X_{c(0)}$ of cement content gradually increase. Compared with the BCS, the ΔX_c of FRS with 0.2%, 0.4%, 0.6% and 0.8% fiber content decreased by 1.09, 1.26, 1.57 and 1.70 on average, and their reduction margin $\Delta X_c/X_{c(0)}$ are 17.23%, 19.00%, 24.27% and 25.34%, respectively. This is because when the fiber content increases, more fibers are randomly distributed in the FRS, the effect of the adhesion, friction, interlocking and confinement between the fiber and the solid particles of VCS could be enhanced, and the palm fiber plays a more important role to the strength of the VCS.

Table 8. Comparison Chart of $X_{c(0)}$, $X_{c(2)}$, ΔX_c and $\Delta X_c/X_{c(0)}$.

$X_{c(0)}/\%$	$W_f = 0.2\%$			$W_f = 0.4\%$			$W_f = 0.6\%$			$W_f = 0.8\%$		
	$X_{c(2)}$	ΔX_c	$\Delta X_c/X_{c(0)}$									
4.8	3.36	1.44	29.91%									
5.0	3.92	1.08	21.56%									
5.2	4.24	0.96	18.39%	3.77	1.43	27.49%	2.11	3.09	59.35%			
5.4	4.50	0.90	16.64%	4.26	1.14	21.18%	3.95	1.45	26.78%	3.46	1.94	35.88%
5.6	4.73	0.87	15.53%	4.56	1.04	18.57%	4.34	1.26	22.58%	4.09	1.51	26.94%
5.8	4.94	0.86	14.77%	4.81	0.99	17.12%	4.61	1.19	20.55%	4.41	1.39	23.89%
6.0	5.15	0.85	14.24%	5.02	0.98	16.26%	4.84	1.16	19.41%	4.66	1.34	22.35%
6.2	5.34	0.86	13.90%	5.22	0.98	15.77%	5.04	1.16	18.78%	4.86	1.34	21.56%
6.4	5.52	0.88	13.74%	5.40	1.00	15.58%	5.21	1.19	18.54%	5.04	1.36	21.30%
6.6	5.69	0.91	13.79%	5.56	1.04	15.69%	5.37	1.23	18.65%	5.18	1.42	21.47%
6.8	5.84	0.96	14.09%	5.70	1.10	16.11%	5.50	1.30	19.12%	5.30	1.50	22.05%
7.0	5.97	1.03	14.68%	5.82	1.18	16.86%	5.60	1.40	19.94%	5.39	1.61	22.99%
7.2	6.08	1.12	15.57%	5.91	1.29	17.92%	5.68	1.52	21.07%	5.46	1.74	24.22%
7.4	6.16	1.24	16.74%	5.98	1.42	19.25%	5.74	1.66	22.45%	5.50	1.90	25.65%
7.6	6.22	1.38	18.16%	6.02	1.58	20.77%	5.78	1.82	23.98%	5.53	2.07	27.21%
7.8	6.26	1.54	19.74%	6.05	1.75	22.41%	5.80	2.00	25.61%	5.55	2.25	28.83%
8.0	6.29	1.71	21.41%	6.07	1.93	24.11%	5.82	2.18	27.27%	5.56	2.44	30.46%
Average value		1.09	17.23%		1.26	19.00%		1.57	24.27%		1.70	25.34%

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928.t008>

Table 9. The W_f and W'_f calculated by theoretical method and interpolation method.

BCS of EF section	$X_{c(0)}/\%$	4.1	4.3	4.5	4.7	4.9	5.1
FRS	W_f	0.038	0.065	0.108	0.178	0.291	0.47
	W'_f	0.04	0.065	0.11	0.185	0.3	0.48
margin of Error		5.0%	0.0%	1.8%	3.8%	3.0%	2.1%

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928.t009>

4.4 The linear interpolation method to calculate the fiber content and cement content of FRS

In theory, the fiber content W_f and cement content $X_{c(2)}$ of the FRS with the same strength of BCS can be calculated through Formula (4) and Formula (7). For convenience, we could look-up the values of the W_f and the $X_{c(2)}$ by Tables 7 and 8, respectively. For the values that cannot be obtained from Tables 7 or 8 (for example, the W_f corresponding to the $X_{c(0)}$ with a value of 4.1 in Table 7 or the $X_{c(2)}$ corresponding to the $X_{c(0)}$ with a value of 5.3 in Table 8), the values of W_f and $X_{c(2)}$ can be calculated by linear interpolation based on the data in Tables 7 and 8.

Table 9 gives the theory value of W_f and the approximative value of W'_f obtained by Formula (4) and linear interpolation, respectively. Table 10 gives the theory value of $X_{c(2)}$ and the approximative value of $X'_{c(2)}$ obtained by Formula (7) and linear interpolation, respectively. The fiber ratio and cement content of the reinforced base material calculated by the interpolation method are recorded as W'_f and $X'_{c(2)}$, respectively.

It can be seen from Table 9, compared with the W_f with theory calculation, the errors of the W'_f range from 0.0% to 5.0%, which are very small. It means that the W_f of FRS can be calculated by the line interpolation method based on the data in Table 5 in practice.

As shown in Table 10, when the cement content $X_{c(0)}$ of the BCS is close to the cement content $X_{c(F)}$ at the critical point F, the error between $X_{c(2)}$ and the $X'_{c(2)}$ is relatively large. In this case, the cement content $X_{c(2)}$ of the FRS shall be calculated according to the theoretical

Table 10. The $X_{c(2)}$ and $X'_{c(2)}$ calculated by theoretical method and interpolation method.

$X_{c(0)}/\%$	FRS											
	$W_f = 0.2\%$			$W_f = 0.4\%$			$W_f = 0.4\%$			$W_f = 0.8\%$		
	$X_{c(2)}$	$X'_{c(2)}$	margin of Error	$X_{c(2)}$	$X'_{c(2)}$	margin of Error	$X_{c(2)}$	$X'_{c(2)}$	Error	$X_{c(2)}$	$X'_{c(2)}$	margin of Error
4.9	3.70	3.64										
5.1	4.10	4.08										
5.3	4.38	4.37	0.5%	4.06	4.01	2.5%	3.63	3.03	30.0%			
5.5	4.62	4.62	0.0%	4.42	4.41	0.5%	4.17	4.14	1.5%	3.86	3.78	4.0%
5.7	4.84	4.84	0.0%	4.69	4.68	0.5%	4.48	4.47	0.5%	4.27	4.25	1.0%
5.9	5.05	5.04	0.5%	4.92	4.92	0.0%	4.73	4.72	0.5%	4.54	4.54	0.0%
6.1	5.24	5.24	0.0%	5.13	5.12	0.5%	4.94	4.94	0.0%	4.77	4.76	0.5%
6.3	5.43	5.43	0.0%	5.31	5.31	0.0%	5.13	5.12	0.5%	4.95	4.95	0.0%
6.5	5.61	5.61	0.0%	5.49	5.48	0.5%	5.29	5.29	0.0%	5.11	5.11	0.0%
6.7	5.77	5.77	0.0%	5.64	5.63	0.5%	5.44	5.43	0.5%	5.25	5.24	0.5%
6.9	5.91	5.91	0.0%	5.77	5.76	0.5%	5.56	5.55	0.5%	5.35	5.35	0.0%
7.1	6.03	6.03	0.0%	5.87	5.86	0.5%	5.65	5.64	0.5%	5.43	5.42	0.5%
7.3	6.12	6.12	0.0%	5.95	5.94	0.5%	5.71	5.71	0.0%	5.48	5.48	0.0%
7.5	6.19	6.19	0.0%	6.00	6.00	0.0%	5.76	5.76	0.0%	5.52	5.52	0.0%
7.7	6.24	6.24	0.0%	6.04	6.04	0.0%	5.79	5.79	0.0%	5.54	5.54	0.0%
7.9	6.28	6.27	0.0%	6.06	6.06	0.0%	5.81	5.81	0.0%	5.56	5.56	0.0%

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928.t010>

method of Formula (7); When the cement content of the BCS is greater than the critical value $X_{c(F)}$ of the cement content, the error between $X_{c(2)}$ and the $X'_{c(2)}$ is small, and the cement content of the FRS also can be obtained by the line interpolation method based on the data in Table 10.

4.5 The deformation characteristics of the FRS under the condition of equal strength

In order to illustrate the effect of the palm fiber substitution for cement on the mechanical properties of BCS under the condition of equal strength, two samples of the BCS and the FRS were selected for comparative analysis. The cement content of the BCS sample (marked as ①) is 8%, and its ultimate strength is 548.4 kPa; the cement content of the FRS sample (marked as ②) is 6%, and its fiber content and ultimate strength are 0.8% and 586.9 kPa, respectively. Obviously, the ultimate strength of sample ② is slightly greater than that of sample ①.

As shown in Fig 4, when the cement content is constant, the ultimate strength of the FRS is positively correlated with the fiber content. Therefore, it can be inferred that the fiber content is less than 0.8% when the cement content of the ideal sample (marked as ③) of the FRS with the same strength as the control sample ① is 6%. Studies have shown that when the cement content of the BCS keeps constant, the higher the fiber content is, the better the ductility and the ability to resist deformation and failure of the VCS are (Huang et al 2021). That is, the ability to resist deformation and failure of the ideal sample ③ is better than that of the sample ②.

Fig 7 shows the stress-strain curves of specimens ① and ② and their failure photos.

As can be observed, the sample ① possesses a softening stress-strain curve, and when its axial strain reaches up to 3%, the sample is damaged. However, the curve of the sample ② is characterized as strain hardening feature, and when the axial strain reaches up to 3%, it enters the stage of plastic deformation. With the further increasing of axial strain (>5%), the strain hardening feature of the sample ② appears gradually, indicating a better ductility of FRS.

Apart from the stress-strain curve, the number of cracks on the surface of the sample ② is obviously less than that of the sample ①. And the length of its cracks are also shorter than

Fig 7. Stress-strain curves and failure photos of BCS sample and FRS sample.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311928.g007>

those of the sample ①, which means that the sample ② has better integrity and structure. Overall, with the comparison of the sample ① and sample ②, it can be concluded that the FRS has better deformation characteristics than the BCS under the condition of equal strength.

In summary, the ability of the BCS sample (①), the FRS sample (②) and the ideal FRS sample (③) to resist deformation and failure from large to small is ③>②>①. This shows that the addition of palm fiber in VCS helped in improving the ability to resist deformation and failure under the condition of equal strength.

5 Conclusion

This paper conducted unconsolidated undrained triaxial shear tests on blank and reinforced VCS under different cement content and fiber ratio factors, and the following main conclusions were obtained.

1. The reinforcement of palm fiber can obviously improve the mechanical properties of VCS. The softening characteristics of the stress-strain curve of the reinforced substrate gradually weaken with the increase of fiber content. The eccentric stress and peak strength of reinforced substrate are higher than those of unreinforced substrate, and increase with the increase of fiber content under the same axial strain variation.
2. The relationship between the peak strength and cement content of VCS can better fitted by the Boltzmann function. There is a critical point $X_c(F)$ when fiber replaces cement under the condition of equal strength. Cement can be completely replaced with palm fiber when the cement content of unreinforced substrate was below $X_c(F)$. While the cement content of unreinforced substrate is higher than $X_c(F)$, cement can be partially reduced through the reinforcement compensation of palm fiber. Under the condition of equal strength, the average decrease of cement content with the increase of fiber content from 0.2% to 0.8% is 17.23%, 19.00%, 24.27% and 25.34%, respectively.
3. The cement content of reinforced substrates can be determined by approximate calculation using an equal strength model or interpolation method in engineering practice.
4. Fibers can not only compensate for the strength loss of the substrate caused by a decrease in cement content, but also improve the ductility of the substrate and enhance its ability to resist deformation and damage.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: Xiaole Huang.

Data curation: Xue An.

Formal analysis: Gang Zeng.

Funding acquisition: Xiaole Huang.

Investigation: Shiyuan Xiong.

Methodology: Gang Zeng.

Project administration: Xiaole Huang, Gang Zeng.

Software: Xiaojun Sun.

Supervision: Xue An.

Validation: Shiyuan Xiong.

Visualization: Xiaojun Sun.

Writing – original draft: Xiaole Huang.

Writing – review & editing: Gang Zeng.

References

1. Bai YX, Liu J, Xiao HL, et al. Soil stabilization using synthetic polymer for soil slope ecological protection. *Engineering Geology*, 2023, 321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enggeo.2023.107155>.
2. Dong TX, Deng YW, Qi GY. Application analysis of ecological slope protection technology for mountain highway slope. *Sustainability in Environment*, 2023, 8(2). <https://doi.org/10.1093/tse/tdaa006>.
3. Su H, Wu DY, Lu YJ, et al. Experimental and numerical study on stability performance of new ecological slope protection using bolt-hinge anchored block. *Ecological Engineering*, 2021, 172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2021.106409>.
4. Ma YF, Bao H, Yan CG, et al. Mechanical properties and microstructure evolution of two ecological slope-protection materials under dry-wet cycles. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 2023, 416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.137833>.
5. Cheng XY, Yang RM, Han Y. Construction method for ecological protection of stone side slopes using composite vegetation concrete. *Scientific reports*, 2023, 13(1):16871–16882. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-43833-0> PMID: 37803103
6. Guo H. Summary of slope ecological protection technology. *Journal of Architectural Research and Development*, 2021, 5(4):9–12. <https://doi.org/10.26689/jard.v5i4.2378>.
7. Su L, Hu B, Xie Q, et al. Experimental and theoretical study of mechanical properties of root-soil interface for slope protection. *Journal of Mountain Science*, 2020, 17(11):2784–2795. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11629-020-6077-4>.
8. Tang W, Mohseni E, Wang Z. Development of vegetation concrete technology for slope protection and greening. *Construction and building materials*, 2018, 179:605–613. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.05.207>.
9. Xia L, Zhao BQ, Luo T, et al. Microbial functional diversity in rhizosphere and non-rhizosphere soil of different dominant species in a vegetation concrete slope. *Biotechnology & biotechnological equipment*, 2022, 36(1):379–388. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13102818.2022.2082319>.
10. Liu D, Liu D, Gao J, et al. Influence of addition of two typical activated carbons on fertility properties and mechanical strength of vegetation concrete under freeze-thaw conditions. *Science of the total environment*, 2022, 838,156446. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.156446> PMID: 35660577
11. Liu D, Xu W, Cheng Z, et al. Improvement test on frost resistance of vegetation-concrete and engineering application of test fruitage. *Environmental earth sciences*, 2013, 69(1):161–170. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-012-1944-0>.
12. Faiz H, Ng S, Rahman M. A state of the art review on the advancement of sustainable vegetation concrete in slope stability. *Construction and building materials*, 2022, 326:126502. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2022.126502>.
13. Huang X, Ding Y, Xu W, et al. Mechanical Performance of Vegetation-Growing Concrete Reinforced by Palm Fibers under Triaxial Compression. *KSCE Journal of Civil Engineering*, 2021(12):4610–4619. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12205-021-2160-9>.
14. Liu D, Zhang B, Yang Y, et al. Effect of organic material type and proportion on the physical and mechanical properties of vegetation-concrete. *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*, 2018, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/3608750>.
15. Wang P, Liu XL, Zeng G, et al. Effects of temperature on the leaching behaviors of Pb from cement stabilization/solidification treated contaminated soil. *Separations*, 2022, 9, 402:1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/separations9120402>.
16. Wang Y, Sun L, Li A, et al. Effect of modified recycled carbon fibers on the conductivity of cement-based materials. *Construction and Building Materials*, 2024, 415. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2024.135033>.
17. Zhang B, Liu D, Su H. Single pullout experiment and reinforcement properties of basalt fiber in vegetation concrete. *Scientific reports*, 2022, 12(1):1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-99269-x>
18. Afrin H. A review on different types soil stabilization techniques. *International Journal of Transportation Engineering and Technology*, 2017, 3(2), 19–24. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ijtet.20170302.12>.

19. Tiwari N, Satyam N, Puppala AJ. Strength and durability assessment of expansive soil stabilized with recycled ash and natural fibers. *Transportation Geotechnics*, 2021, 29, 100556. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trgeo.2021.100556>.
20. Xu H, Guo J, Yuan K, et al. Radial microbial grouting method by intubation for sandy soil reinforcement: experimental and numerical investigation. *Construction and Building Materials*, 2023, 375, 130960. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.130960>.
21. Li J, Tang C, Wang D, et al. Effect of discrete fiber reinforcement on soil tensile strength. *Journal of Rock Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering*, 2014, 6(2), 133–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrmge.2014.01.003>
22. Sadrolodabae P, Claramunt J, Ardanuy M, et al. A Textile Waste Fiber-Reinforced Cement Composite: Comparison between Short Random Fiber and Textile Reinforcement. *Materials*, 2021, 14 (13):3742. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14133742> PMID: 34279314
23. Liu B, Zhang XY, Ye JP, et al. Mechanical properties of hybrid fiber reinforced coral concrete. *Case Studies in Construction Materials*, 2022, 16: e00865. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscm.2021.e00865>.
24. Raj B, Sathyan D, Madhavan ML, et al. Mechanical and durability properties of hybrid fiber reinforced foam concrete. *Construction and Building Materials*, 2020, 245, 118373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.118373>.
25. Sharma R, Senthil K. An investigation on mechanical and microstructural properties of hybrid fiber reinforced concrete with manufactured sand and recycled coarse aggregate. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 2023, 69, 106236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2023.106236>.
26. Zhong YQ, Cai GH, Zeng G. The effect of initial water content and density on the swelling-shrinkage and cracking characteristics of compacted clay. *Separations*, 2022, 9(12), 424:1–17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/separations9120424>.